

THE LIFE AND WORK OF AJINIYAZ QOSIBAY OĞLI

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Abstract. *This article discusses the life and work of Ajiniyaz Qosibay oğli, the celebration of the poet's 175th anniversary, and his cultural and educational work.*

Keywords: *poet, science, lyrics, madrasa, folklore genres.*

ЖИЗНЬ И ТВОРЧЕСТВО АЖИНИЯЗА КОСИБАЯ ОГЛЫ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются жизнь и творчество Ажинияза Косибая оглы, празднование 175-летия поэта, его культурно-просветительская деятельность.*

Ключевые слова: *поэт, наука, лирика, медресе, фольклорные жанры.*

Ajiniyaz was born in 1824 on the southern shore of the Aral Sea, in the village of Qamish Bugat, Muynak district, on the banks of the Amu Darya, in the areas inhabited by the Ashamayli-Kiyat tribe of the Karakalpaks[2][3]. Ajiniyaz's father Qosibay, and his brothers Baltabek and Akjigit were heroes of their time. His mother Nazira was a eloquent, charming lady.

Ajiniyaz was interested in science since childhood. He first studied at the Khojamurad imam madrasah, and then, after the death of his mother, he took lessons from his uncle Elmurad. In addition to attending classes, the future poet was also engaged in rewriting books, which made him famous. At the age of 16, he rewrote several poems by Alisher Navoi. Ajinyoz continued his studies in Khiva. In the ancient cultural center of Khorezm, he studied first at the Shergozikhan madrasah, where the Turkmen classical poet Makhtumkuli studied, and then at the Kutlimurat Inak madrasah[2]. Today, at the entrance to the madrasah, you can see the inscription: "Here in 1840-1845, the poet Ajinyoz Qosiboy oglu studied." Along with spiritual sciences, Ajinyaz studied the poetry of classical Eastern poets such as Navoi, Hafiz, Sa'di Shirazi, and Fuzuli at the Kutlimurot Inaq Madrasah, which greatly influenced his advanced lyricism.

After graduating from the Kutlimurot Inaq Madrasah, Ajinyaz returned to his village, but soon left for Kazakhstan again and stayed there for a year. Upon his return, he married a girl named Khamra from the Ashmayli tribe, and his wife had two sons and a daughter. His descendants now live in the Kungirat, Qanlikol, and Shumanay districts and the city of Nukus.

The Kungarat Uprising of 1858–1859, one of the most important events in the history of the peoples living in the Khorezm oasis, had a great influence on Ajinyaz's poetic nature. The patriot and scholar could not remain indifferent to this event, but rather preferred to take an active part in it. Then, as one of the leaders of the uprising, he was exiled to Turkmenistan by the Khiva government[4]. During his exile, the poet translated many of Makhtumkuli's poems into the

Karakalpak language[3].

Three years later, Ajinyaz returned home. Due to circumstances, he went to Kazakhstan. It is believed that in 1864, during a trip to Kazakhstan, he participated in a lyrical competition called "Kiz Mengesh" with a Kazakh poet. Compared to other contemporary folklore genres of the region, the aytsuv was especially popular. It was published in the Tashkent newspaper "Turkestanskiye vedomosti" in 1878. He died in 1878[2].

He was one of the first among the Karakalpak intellectuals to achieve the rank of akhund. He was fluent in Uzbek, Kazakh, and Turkmen[3]. About 100 poems and epics have come down to us from Ajinyaz's literary heritage. His poems glorify the ideas of patriotism and humanity. A.'s humanistic ideas and philosophical views are expressed in such works as "Need", "Will", "If Not", "Good", "Guys". His works are widely known among the people. The work "Speaking with Girl Mengesh" (1878) is famous. The writer K. Sultanov wrote the novel "Ajiniyoz" (1967) about his life, and the poet I. Yusupov created the libretto for the opera "Ajiniyoz" (1989). His works were published in Uzbek ("Selected Works", 1962, etc.).

In 1999, the 175th anniversary of the birth of Ajiniyoz was widely celebrated in Uzbekistan. A square named after the poet was built in a picturesque place in the city of Nukus and a monument to Ajiniyoz was erected.

The 200th anniversary of the birth of Ajiniyoz Qosiboy oglu is widely celebrated in Uzbekistan. The presidential decree "On the wide celebration of the 200th anniversary of the birth of the famous Karakalpak poet and thinker Ajiniyoz Qosiboy oglu" was adopted.

A program of measures is approved to celebrate the 200th anniversary of the poet's birth and widely promote his creative heritage, which includes the following tasks:

Publishing the poet's collection "Selected Works" in Uzbek and Karakalpak languages;

Creating stage plays dedicated to the poet's life and work and the art and journalistic film "Ajinyoz" and organizing their presentations;

Organizing a museum of the poet at the Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajinyoz;

Beautifying the grave of Ajinyoz Qosiboy oglu in the Muynak district and erecting a monument to it, and establishing an eco-park named after Ajinyoz Qosiboy oglu in this district;

Organizing solemn literary and artistic commemorative evenings dedicated to the 200th anniversary of the poet's birth in November 2024 at the Alisher Navoi and Berdaq State Academic Theaters.

The President's decree "On the broad celebration of the 200th anniversary of the birth of the outstanding Karakalpak poet and thinker Ajinyoz Kosibay ugli" has been signed. This was reported by the President's press service. According to the decree, the poet's collection "Selected Works" will be published in the Uzbek and Karakalpak languages. Artistic, scientific and popular

works dedicated to his life and work will be reprinted and presented.

According to the state order, stage plays dedicated to the life and activities of Ajiniyoz Kosiboy's son and the feature-publicist film "Ajiniyoz" will be created. In the city of Nukus, a competition of young artists of the country, a competition of essays dedicated to the life and work of the son of Ajiniyoz Kosiboy will be held among students of creative schools on the theme "Say, you from the songs of Ajiniyoz".

In September 2024, an exhibition of books, works of fine art, and examples of folk applied art dedicated to the life and work of Ajiniyoz Kosiboy ugli will be held in the Central Exhibition Hall of the Academy of Arts. In October, international scientific and practical conferences will be organized at Karakalpak State University and the Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi on the topic of studying the literary heritage of Ajiniyoz Kosiboy ugli.

A poet's museum will be established at Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz. The grave of the son of Ajiniyaz Kosiboy in Moynaq district will be beautified and a monument will be erected to him. An ecopark named after the son of Ajiniyaz Kosiboy will be established in this district.

Meetings and literary evenings dedicated to the 200th anniversary of the birth of the son of Ajiniyaz Qosiboy will be organized in higher and secondary special, professional, general secondary educational institutions, labor unions and neighborhoods of the country with the participation of famous writers and poets, scientists.

In November 2024, solemn literary and artistic memorial evenings dedicated to the 200th anniversary of the birth of Ajiniyoz Kusiboy ugli will be held at the Alisher Navoi State Academic Bolshoi Theater of Uzbekistan and the Berdakh Karakalpak State Academic Theater.

REFERENCES

1. Ajiniyaz Kosibay-Uli. Biography of the Poet. <http://www.ndpi.uz/img/menu/26/ajiniyaz.htm> (Wayback Machine saytida 2018-09-25 sanasida arxivlangan) (accessed on 2018-08-28)
2. 2,0 2,1 2,2 Nizami Məmmədov-Tağısoy. "Qaraqalpaq ədəbiyyatı." (Wayback Machine saytida 2021-11-01 sanasida arxivlangan) Bakı, "Elm və təhsil", 2015, səh. 226, anl.az (Ozarbayjoncha)
3. 3,0 3,1 3,2 Nizami Məmmədov-Tağısoy. "Qaraqalpaq ədəbiyyatı." (Wayback Machine saytida 2021-11-01 sanasida arxivlangan) Bakı, "Elm və təhsil", 2015, səh. 227, anl.az (Ozarbayjoncha)

4. Nizami Məmmədov-Tağısoy. "Qaraqalpaq ədəbiyyatı." (Wayback Machine saytida 2021-11-01 sanasida arxivlangan) Bakı, "Elm və təhsil", 2015, səh. 228, anl.az (Ozarbayjoncha)
5. Omarova A. SCHOOL CHEERS THROUGH MUSIC PROFESSIONAL DIRECTION //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 10. – C. 151-156.
6. Omarova A., Shamurodova M. APPLICATION OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS WHEN TEACHING A MUSIC LESSON //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 12. – C. 185-189.